

TARIX FANINI O'QITISHDA DARSЛИKLAR BILAN ISHLASH MASALASI

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani 2 son kasb
hunar maktabi tarix fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada tarix fanini o'qitishda darslikdan foydalanish va qo'shimcha manbalar bilan ishlashning afzalliklari, o'quvchilarga bilim berishda tasavvO'rga keng yo'l ochish masalasi haqida qisqacha fikrlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarix, darslik, matn, bilim, o'quvchi

Аннотация: В статье даются краткие размышления о преимуществах использования учебников и работы с дополнительными источниками в преподавании истории, а также вопросе открытия широкого пути воображению при обучении учащихся.

Ключевые слова: История, учебник, текст, знания, ученик.

Abstract: The article briefly discusses the advantages of using textbooks and working with additional sources in teaching history, and the issue of opening up a wide field for imagination in imparting knowledge to students.

Keywords: History, textbook, text, knowledge, student

O'rta ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida tarix o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan matnlarga - darslik matni, tarixiy xujjatlar, asarlar, ilmiy -ommabop va badiiy, tarixiy adabiyotlar va boshkalar kiradi. Bosma matnlar o'quvchilar tarixiy bilimlarining asosiy manbai bulgani kabi o'qituvchining bilim manbaini, bayonining asosini tashkil etadi. Tabiiydirki, o'qituvchi shu manbalardan tO'rli va unumli foydalangan takdirdagina, uning bayoni zamon talablariga, umuman O'rta

ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimidagi tarix ta'limining talablariga javob berishi, o'qituvchi bayonining o'quvchilarga tushunarli, mazmundor, marokdi va ilmiy jixatdan ishonarli, obrazli va ta'sirli bulishi mumkin. Shuningdek matnlarlar ustida ishlash o'quvchilar bilimini kengaytiradi, tarixiy fakt va xodisalarning moxiyatini, ularning

konuniyatlarini chuqurroq tushunib olishlariga yordam beradi, milliy istiqlol tarbiyasi shakllanadi, tarixiy fikrlash xosil buladi, ular tarixiy voqealarga baxo berishga o'rganadilar. O'rta ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilar xar xil matnlar ustida ishlab mustakil ish ko'rish malakasini xosil kiladilar va tarixiy tadkikot ishlarining dastlabki metodlari bilan amaliy ravishda tanishadilar.

O'qituvchi o'quv dastur talabiga muvofiq tarix darsligi matnini mazmuniga darslik matnini asos kilib oladi. O'qituvchi uzining bayonini boshka ,matnlar sosida yanada aniklashtiradi ■ va boyitadi. Darslik matni o'quvchilarning darsda va darsdan tashkari taryxni) O'rganish, o'zlashtirish va uni esda saqlab qolishining, bilish faoliyatining, ijodiy izlanish ishlarini olib borishning muxim manbaidir. Matn va ulardagi savollar, topshiriqlar tarix kursining mazmunini ijodiy uzlashtirishga va olingan bilimlarni xayotda qo'llashga o'rgatadi.

Darslik matni ustidagi ishlash o'quv materialini uzlashtirish va uni esda saqlab kolish, o'quv tekstini taxlil kilish va undan tarixiy voqea, xodisalarning muxim belgilarini topish, faktik materiallarni va tarixiy faktlarning muxim belgilarini bir-biriga takkoshlash, aniklashtirish va umumlashtirish kabi turli xil maqsadlarda olib boriladi.

Tarixiy xujjat, avvalo, o'qituvchining bayonini aniqdashtirish, chuqurlatish va unga aninlik kiritish uchun xizmat qiladi, bayonning ishonchli va emosional bulishini ta'minlaydi, utmishning yorkin obrazlarini, tarixiy voqealarning yaxlit manzarasini gavdalanitirishga, O'rganilayotgan davr xususiyatlarini anglab olishga yordam beradi. Xujjat ustida ishlash o'quvchilarni faktlar va xodisalarni mustakil ravishda aniklashga, ularni puxta anglab olib, xulosalar chikarishga o'rgatadi. Shu

bilan birga xujjat ma'lum vaziyatni aniqlashga, axamiyatini bilib olishga, tarixni obyektiv nuqsgai nazardan tushunishga yordam beradiki, ularning bilish faoliyatini, fikrlashini faollashtiradi, o'quv ishlari faoliyatining yangi usullari bilan qurollantiradi, zarur bo'lgan malaka davrimizning ijtimoiy-siyosiy xarakterdagi xujjatlarini ukib, tushunib olish malakasini xosil qiladi.

Tarixiy xujjatlar bilan ishlashning yana bir muxim tomoni shundaki, bu ish o'quvchilarni tarixiy tadqiqot metodining elementlari bilan tanishtiradi xamda ularni tarixiy xujjatlarga tankidiy qarashga o'rgatadi. O'rta ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida ta'limning yangi mazmuni amalga oshishi munosabati bilan tarix o'qitishda tarixiy xujjatlarning axamiyati yanada oshdi. Yangi dastur asosida yozilgan darsliklar mazmunining asosiy qismini tarixiy xujjatlar tashkil etadi. Dars va darsdan tashqari mashgulotlarda xam tarixiy xujjatlar bilan ishlash zaruriy bo'lib qoldi.

Shuning uchun ham bu ish O'rta ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida tajribasida ommaviy tus oldi.

Darsliklardagi tarixiy xujjatlar xar bir sinfdagi o'quvchilarning yoshi, bilim saviyasi, usha sinfda o'rganiladigan tarix kursining xususiyatlariga qarab kiritilgan. Shu sababdan darsliklardagi tarixiy xujjatlar o'zlarining xarakteri, ko'lami va mazmuni jixdtidan bir-biridan farq qiladi.

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